

EFFECT OF THE PRE-CONSOLIDATION PROCESS ON QUALITY AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MONO AND MULTI-MATERIAL LAMINATES BASED ON THERMOPLASTIC UD TAPES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, at first the effects of the main processing parameters characterizing the pre-consolidation step using a double belt press – temperature, pressure and belt-speed – on the apparent inter laminar shear strength (A-ILSS) of tape-based 8 layers PA6/GF40 (vol.%) preforms are investigated. Based on these results, three different pre-consolidation qualities are defined and their effects on the end-consolidated laminates are determined and compared to UD tape based laminates produced without employing a pre-consolidation step. Secondly, the differences in the pre-consolidation step of mono- and multi-material tape based laminates with PA6/CF49 (vol.%) UD tapes are pointed out.

The investigations show that the heat related process parameters – belt speed/processing time and temperature during pre-consolidation - are mainly influencing the welding-quality of the UD tape lay-ups and thereby the A-ILSS. In contrast, only minor influence of the pressure can be determined within the considered range. A decrease in the belt speed (2 m/min to 0.2 m/min) leads to an improved welding of the layers and thereby to an increase of the A-ILSS from 13 MPa to 35 MPa. Moreover, a correlation of the A-ILSS with the applied heating temperature is established: The A-ILSS increases by 31 % with rising temperature from 230 to 250 °C. These findings are also correlated with the morphology of the preforms. The heating of the multi-material laminates occurs faster, which can be traced back to the higher thermal conductivity of carbon fiber reinforced tape layers. This leads to a better fusion of the layers, which can be verified by microscopic pictures.

When comparing the variations in the preforming qualities with the resulting flexural properties of end-consolidated UD laminates, no significant influences can be found for mono-material designs. Laminates without pre-consolidation show comparable flexural properties. On the contrary, an increase in the flexural properties of the multi-material laminates (up to 25 %) can be achieved by the pre-consolidation process.

1 INTRODUCTION

The primary steps for the processing of unidirectional fiber-reinforced tapes (UD tapes) are tape lay-up, Pre-consolidation and Compression Injection Molding [1-2]. Thereby, load-optimized and high-strength structural components with minimum material scrap can be produced in cycle times between 60 and 90 s. It is well-known, that the pre-consolidation of a stacked layer of tapes is necessary as a part of preforming [3-5], in order to avoid air entrapments in the end-consolidated laminate after compression and injection molding [6-7]. But it hasn't been quantitatively investigated yet, how the process parameters of the pre-consolidated step and the resulting preform quality, affect the mechanical properties of the end-consolidated laminate.

This study has been carried out in order to understand the pre-consolidation step itself and the influence of its main parameters (heating temperature, belt speed, consolidation pressure) on the preform quality and on the mechanical properties of end-consolidated laminates. The influence of the

process parameters on the welding quality is physically based on the heating input, contact pressure and the molecular inter diffusion [8-13].

Glass fiber (GF) reinforced tapes as well as a combination of glass and carbon fiber (CF) based tapes – so called multi-material lay-ups – were considered in this study, both based on a PA6 matrix.

The correlation between pre-consolidation quality and the resulting mechanical properties of end-consolidated laminates is established for multi-material lay-up designs as well.

2 MATERIALS

For the investigations in this study, glass and carbon fiber Polyamide 6 UD tapes were used. Table 1 presents the major characteristics of the tapes.

Material	Thickness (mm)	Fiber Content (vol.-%)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Thermal conductivity at 25 °C \perp to fiber orientation (W/mK)
PA6/GF	0.25	40	35	1283	0.46
PA6/CF	0.16	49	103	1211	0.61

Table 1: Major characteristics of UD tapes used for multi-material laminates in this work

The mono-material lay-ups were manually built up with a unidirectional fiber orientation consisting of 8 glass fiber UD tape layers and were locally welded with an ultrasonic welding system (type: SoniPro 35/1000, MS Spaichingen GmbH, Spaichingen – Germany). For the multi-material lay-ups a specific number of surface layers has been replaced by carbon fiber UD tapes, in order to achieve a “sandwich design”.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

The thermal properties of the matrix system of the UD tapes were primarily analysed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), employing a DSC 1 (Mettler Toledo, Greifensee – Switzerland). The UD tapes were dried 4 hours at 80 °C under vacuum and the measurements were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere. The samples (weight: 10 ± 3 mg) were heated up to 280 °C and after a holding time of 5 minutes cooled down to room temperature. The chosen heating and cooling rate was 10 K/min.

The UD-tape stacks with a size of 166 x 210 mm² were pre-consolidated in a double belt press (type: KFK-E 1700, Maschinenfabrik Herbert Meyer GmbH, Roetz – Germany) with various parameters. The heating line of the double belt press, perpendicular to the direction of material flow, has a length of 1350 mm and is separated in three zones that are all heated to the same temperature level. In order to protect the PTFE belts of the machine from the welding spots, a PTFE foil (thickness: 0.2 mm) was applied on both sides of the lay-up. The stacks were end-consolidated to laminates (dimensions: 210 x 210 mm²) in a laboratory press (type: RMV 125/1 HT, Lauffer GmbH & Co. KG, Lilienthal - Germany). Before pressing the pre-consolidated preforms, they were preheated in a convection oven (type: N60/85 HA, Nabertherm GmbH) at 300 °C for 10 min. The adjusted mold temperature was 200 °C and 10 bar pressure was applied. Generally, the samples were finally cut out with a waterjet cutting system (type: Flow Mach 2, Flow Europe GmbH, Weiterstadt – Germany). In order to evaluate the influence of the main pre-consolidation parameters – belt speed, heating temperature and consolidation pressure – on the resulting preform quality, the software MODDE PRO (Version 11, Sartorius Stedim Biotech GmbH – Germany) was used for design of experiment. The analysed parameters are listed in Table 2.

Factor	Lower limit	Upper limit
Belt speed	0.2 m/min	2.0 m/min
Heating temperature	230 °C	250 °C
Consolidation pressure	1 bar	4.8 bar

Table 2: Parameter range for design of experiment analysis

The lower limit of belt speed and the upper limit of heating temperature were chosen based on the technical limits of the double belt press.

Preforms with a size of 165 x 165 mm² were processed. The temperature profile was measured during the pre-consolidation process with 3 temperature sensors (type: K, TC Mess- und Regeltechnik GmbH, Moenchengladbach – Germany). The sensors were positioned between layer 1/2, 4/5 and 7/8 in each stack. The data was recorded with a temperature measurement system (type: Almemo 5990-2, Ahlborn Mess- und Regelungstechnik GmbH, Ilmenau – Germany). For the evaluation of the pre-consolidation quality and the quality of end-consolidated laminates, the apparent interlaminar shear strength (A-ILSS) and the flexural properties were determined. Generally, the samples were dried before testing at 80 °C for at least 4 hours.

The A-ILSS was determined by the short beam shear test according to DIN EN ISO 2563. The samples were conditioned and tested under standard climate conditions (ambient temperature: 23 °C; relative humidity: 55 %) on a universal testing machine (type: Z020, Zwick GmbH & Co. KG, Ulm - Germany) with a 20 kN load cell. The software testXpert II V3.3 was used for evaluation. The sample geometry was chosen following the testing standard as 20 mm x 10 mm x 2 mm³. The support distance was adjusted for each laminate according to the varying thickness of the specific lay-up design based on the ratio that is given by the standard (support distance / laminate thickness: 5/1). The deflection was detected by the cross head position of the testing machine. A cross head speed of 1 mm/min was adjusted.

The flexural properties of the preforms and laminates were determined using a 3-point bending test according to the DIN EN ISO 14125. The tests were done under standard climate conditions (ambient temperature: 23 °C; relative humidity: 50 %) on a universal testing machine (type: Z050, Zwick GmbH & Co. KG, Ulm - Germany) with a 50 kN load cell. The software testXpert II V3.3 was used for evaluation. The sample geometry was chosen following the material class III of the testing standard as 60 x 15 x 2 mm³. The support distance was adjusted for each laminate according to the varying thickness of the specific lay-up design based on the ratio that is given by the standard (support distance / laminate thickness: 20/1). The deflection was detected by the cross head position of the testing machine. A cross head speed of 1 mm/min was set.

Microscopic investigations were undertaken using optical light microscope (type: Axioskop 2 MAT, Carl Zeiss AG, Oberkochen – Germany).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALOMETRY

Three samples of each UD tape type were analysed by DSC. One of the resulting curves of each material is shown in Figure 1. The softening range of the PA6/GF tapes is between 200 and 226 °C (± 2 °C). The heat flow peak is at 221.8 °C (± 0.9 °C). The softening range [195 – 224 °C (± 2 °C)] as well as the heat flow peak (219.9 °C (± 0.8 °C)) of the PA6/CF tape are significantly lower.

Figure 1: DSC curves of PA6/GF (left) and PA6/CF (right) UD tapes. Second heating curve is plotted; Heating and cooling rate: 10 K/min.

4.2 PRE-CONSOLIDATION TEMPERATURE CURVES

The temperature profile of the preforms during the pre-consolidation process was captured in order to identify possible inhomogeneities. At a belt speed of 0.2 and 1.1 m/min short before the calender roll of the double belt press no significant temperature difference could be determined between the outer layers and the center of the preform. Only for preforms that were pre-consolidated with a belt speed of 2.0 m/min, a rising temperature delta of 2, 6 and 10 K with elevated heating temperature (230, 240, 250 °C) was detected.

Figure 2: Influence of belt speed and heating temperature on the temperature profile in the center layer of mono-material preforms. Left: heating temperature – 240 °C, consolidation pressure – 1 bar; Right: belt speed – 0.2 m/min, consolidation pressure – 1 bar

In Figure 2 the dependency of the temperature profile on the belt speed and heating temperature is shown. The temperature in the middle layer is plotted. There is a significant influence of the belt speed on the resulting heating rate. At belt speeds of 1.1 and 2.0 m/min the heating rate is between 2 and 3 K/s and the adjusted heating temperature of 240 °C is not reached. The difference to the target temperature is 14 K for a belt speed of 1.1 m/min and 34 K for 2.0 m/min. With a belt speed of 0.2 m/min a lower heating rate of around 1.2 K/s is detected and the target temperature of 240 °C is reached after 165 s. Then regulation problems of the double belt press can be seen, that leads to a fluctuation of the temperature in a range of circa ± 10 K.

The adjusted heating temperature has no significant influence on the heating rate (see Figure 2, right). With the consolidation step under the calender role, the cooling process starts.

4.3 ANALYSING PRE-CONSOLIDATION QUALITY

The investigation of the pre-consolidation has indicated that there is only a slight increase of the consolidation pressure on the A-ILSS of the pre-consolidated mono-material preforms (see Figure 3). The differences in the A-ILSS value are within the standard deviation. By contrast, the resulting A-ILSS is tremendously affected by an increasing belt speed.

Figure 3: Influence of consolidation pressure (left: temperature – 240 °C, belt speed – 1.1 m/min) and belt speed (right: temperature 240 °C, pressure – 2.9 bar) on the A-ILSS of PA6/GF (40 vol.%) preforms during pre-consolidation

At a belt speed of 2.0 m/min the A-ILSS is more than 61 % lower compared to the value at 0.2 m/min. This clearly proves that temperature has a major effect on the A-ILSS. Since the temperature impact in combination with high pressure leads to matrix flow and to a fiber displacement, a lower consolidation pressure should be preferred.

Moreover, Figure 4 illustrates the effect of the adjusted heating temperature on the A-ILSS at a belt speed of 0.2 m/min and a low pressure of 1 bar.

Figure 4: Influence of heating temperature (belt speed – 0.2 m/min, pressure – 1.0 bar) on the A-ILSS of PA6/GF (40 vol.%) preforms during pre-consolidation

An increase of the A-ILSS by more than 33 % can be determined, when comparing a heating temperature of 230 and 250 °C. Thereby, it is confirmed that the heat related process parameters have the strongest influence on the A-ILSS.

Figure 5: Cross section of preforms pre-consolidated with a belt speed of 0.2 m/min (left) and 2.0 m/min (right) (consolidation pressure: 1 bar; heating temperature: 230 °C).

The effect of the heat impact on the microstructure is shown in Figure 5. The preforms that were pre-consolidated at a belt speed of 0.2 m/min exhibit a homogenous microstructure. All layers of the stack are welded with each other and no boundaries can be determined. In contrast, the cross section of the rapidly pre-consolidated show significant air pockets and the layers are not smoothly welded. The correlation of these microstructures with the resulting A-ILSS (left: 35 MPa \pm 3 MPa, right: 13 \pm 3 MPa) shows the sensitiveness of the A-ILSS to preform defects and proves its suitability of the A-ILSS as an indicator for the welding quality. Based on the parameter analysis and the presented results, three different pre-consolidation qualities were defined (see Table 3).

Pre-consolidation quality	Consolidation pressure [bar]	Belt speed [m/min]	Heating temperature [°C]	A-ILSS [MPa]
Bad	4.8	2.0	230	10
Good	2.9	1.1	240	33
Best	1	0.2	250	47

Table 3: Parameter set-ups of three different pre-consolidation qualities of mono-material PA6/GF preforms

By taking a closer look to the heating process during the pre-consolidation step, a better understanding for the different pre-consolidation qualities can be gained. In Figure 6 a correlation of the time above the softening temperature in the core layer of a lay-up with the resulting A-ILSS is plotted.

Figure 6: Correlation of the time above the softening temperature during pre-consolidation and the resulting A-ILSS of 8 layer UD mono-material stacks

The Temperature at which the melting of the crystalline areas begins (see Figure 1) was defined as softening temperature. The results can be described by the regression function with K_x as a constant of proportionality:

$$A - ILSS = K_x \cdot (t_{above\ softening\ temperature})^{0.31} \quad (1)$$

This function correlates in a good approximation with the model for isotherm polymer bonding processes of Jud et al. [14] and Wool/O'Connor [15]:

$$\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{\infty}} = \left[\frac{t}{T_r} \right]^{0.25} \xrightarrow{for\ \sigma_{\infty} \cdot T_r^{-0.25} = K_y} \sigma = K_y \cdot t^{0.25} \quad (2)$$

σ_{∞} : Stress at break for compact material; T_r : Material constant;
 K_y : Constant of proportionality

Since the pre-consolidation is not an isotherm process the exponent is not exactly the same. Nevertheless, based on this mathematical similarity it can be derived, that the welding of tape layers during the pre-consolidation step is based on an inter molecular diffusion process. Thus, with increasing belt speed and heating temperature, the diffusion time increases and the welding quality and thereby the A-ILSS is improved. Based on equation 2 the consolidation pressure has no influence on the welding process (see chapter 4.2).

By contrast, carbon fiber UD tape layers lead to higher total thermal conductivity of the lay-up and thereby to a more efficient welding process. Combined with the high stiffness of the carbon fibers, it leads to higher A-ILSS values of the preforms at similar pre-consolidation parameters (see Figure 9).

Nevertheless, the maximum A-ILSS value of end-consolidated multi-material laminates is approximately 10 % lower than the best mono-material laminate. Residual stresses that emerge during consolidation and are caused by different thermal expansion behavior of glass and carbon fibers can be the reason for reduced A-ILSS values [16]. The fracture toughness of materials is negatively influenced by thermal residual stresses and furthermore the shear properties are reduced [17-19].

4.4 DIFFERENCES BETWEEN MONO- AND MULTI-MATERIAL PREFORMS

UD tapes with carbon fiber reinforcement are thinner and have higher thermal conductivity (see Table 1). These properties lead to a faster heating and cooling of the multi-material lay-up and a higher maximum temperature. This theory is proved by temperature profiles of both lay-ups illustrated in Figure 7. The achieved maximum temperature of the multi-material laminate is 234 °C compared to 226 °C of the mono-material lay-up. Nevertheless, no significant difference in the welding quality can be identified when comparing the microscopic images of the cross section of both laminates that are

shown in Figure 8. There are holes and unwelded layers visible on both cross sections. Since there are just small differences the pre-consolidation qualities defined for mono-material laminates were adapted to the multi-material preforms. The parameters and the corresponding A-ILSS values are summarized in Table 4. A comparison of the resulting A-ILSS of mono and multi-material preforms pre-consolidated with the defined parameter set-ups (bad/good/best) is plotted in Figure 9.

Figure 7: Temperature profiles of mono-material and multi-material tape lay-up during pre-consolidation (heating temperature: 240 °C; belt speed: 1.1 m/min). Temperature measured in the center layer.

Figure 8: Cross section of pre-consolidated mono-material (left) and multi-material laminate (right). Both processed with a belt speed of 2.0 m/min, heating temperature of 230 °C and consolidation pressure of 4.8 bar)

Pre-consolidation quality	Consolidation pressure [bar]	Belt speed [m/min]	Heating temperature [°C]	A-ILSS [MPa]
Bad	4.8	2.0	230	26
Good	2.9	1.1	240	47
Best	1	0.2	250	53

Table 4: Parameter set-ups of three different pre-consolidation qualities for multi-material preforms

Figure 9: A-ILSS of mono and multi-material preforms pre-consolidated with the defined parameter set-ups (see Table 3 and Table 4)

4.5 INFLUENCE OF PRE-CONSOLIDATION QUALITY ON END-CONSOLIDATED LAMINATES

The influence of the pre-consolidation quality of the preforms is analyzed by determining the defect-sensitive A-ILSS and the flexural properties of the end-consolidated laminates. The A-ILSS of the end-consolidated laminates can be improved up to 8 % by the pre-consolidation step compared to a laminate without pre-consolidation (see Figure 10). The best pre-consolidation quality is not leading to the laminate with the highest A-ILSS value. In contrast, for multi-material laminates, the best preform quality as well leads to the best A-ILSS in the end-consolidated laminate.

Figure 10: Influence of the pre-consolidation quality on the A-ILSS of mono- and multi-material laminates

The increase compared to the laminates without pre-consolidation is more than 13 % and can be traced back to a better fusion of the center layers of the laminate. Figure 11 shows the influence of the pre-consolidation quality on the flexural properties.

Figure 11: Influence of the pre-consolidation quality on the flexural properties of mono- and multi-material laminates

With regards to the mono-material lay-ups no significant impact can be detected, in other words, there is no positive influence of the pre-consolidation step on the resulting flexural properties of the laminates. On the contrary, the pre-consolidation step has a significant effect on the flexural properties of multi-material laminates. The flexural modulus is increased by more than 25 % and the flexural strength up to 9%, combined with a tremendously reduced standard deviation.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a correlation of the pre-consolidation quality with the resulting mechanical properties of end-consolidated mono- and multi-material laminates is established. In both cases an influence could be determined.

That's why in further studies the residual stresses in multi-material laminates have to be reduced by controlling the thermal conditions during the end-consolidation, in order to improve the mechanical performance.

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